

**CHARACTERISTICS OF FORMING THE MARKETING
STRATEGY IN ENTERPRISES**

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It is difficult to imagine the fundamental basis of socio-economic reforms carried out in our country without entrepreneurship, factor and business qualities. the widespread development of free market relations is reflected in people's lives, lifestyles, spiritual and practical skills. At the same time, we are facing a number of problems during these historical reforms.

One of them is to anticipate the changes and opportunities that will occur and develop business policies and strategies. It is necessary for enterprises and their managers not only to pay attention to the changes in the environment, but also to anticipate, coordinate and adapt these changes to the company's goals and external conditions based on scientifically based methods.

Statistical data show that as a result of the proper organization of an effective marketing strategy, 256.7 trillion won by republican enterprises in January-September 2023. Soums worth of industrial products were produced, and compared to January-September 2022, the physical volume index of industrial production was 97.3%. The industry producing the largest share in the structure of industrial production accounted for its share in the total industrial production (82.6%).

At a time when the economy of our country is developing at a rapid pace, the role of the industrial sector is of great importance today. Innovative development of the industrial sector, provision of equipment and technologies in accordance with world requirements, expansion of export production in this sector is one of the requirements of the time.

In order to ensure the consistent and stable development of product competitiveness in industrial enterprises, the development and precise definition of carefully and comprehensively based measures, important tasks and directions, programs of economic development at various levels for the next period is a guarantee of success.

Marketing is the organization of production and sale of goods with a reasonable study and preliminary assessment of the market situation, as well as the organization of good profit in this regard, and is an important element of the market economy. Marketing activities are carried out through special marketing programs and strategies. They include measures such as improving the quality of goods based on the study of buyers and competitors, changing the price of goods, conducting advertising, studying the demand for goods, delivering goods on time, and providing services that are acceptable to customers. Production adapts to rapidly changing market demand through marketing and achieves a certain effect.

Strategic planning in marketing is a clearly expressed statement of the enterprise, based on the goals, it develops a plan for the development of the business portfolio and a growth strategy, and applies it in life and practice. F. Kotler writes about the strategic planning of the company's activities: "It is a management process of applying strategic compatibility between the goals of the company and its opportunities in the field of marketing."

The concept of strategy in marketing is enriched and clarified by certain concepts in terms of its essence in terms of marketing and business. At the same time, I.A. Nasriddinova and A.M. Akhmedov highlighted procedures in four groups in their research on business strategy.

1. Rules for evaluating the results of the enterprise's current and prospective activities. The qualitative aspects of the evaluation criteria are determined by the goal (orientation), and the quantitative aspect by the tasks.

2. The general rules of the enterprise's relations with the external environment, that is, the general rules about what products and technologies to

enter the market, how to exchange products, how to fight with competitors and achieve speed in relation to them.

The development of market relations requires a transition from reactive management to strategic management. This applies not only to certain management systems, but also to the processes of evaluating and selecting management models and defining conceptual directions in marketing applications.

In the development of the marketing management system, strategy and models, it is important not only to evaluate the current possibilities of using the marketing system, but also to evaluate the inclusion of marketing elements in the management system, which allows the adaptation of marketing management to the changing economic environment. The strategy of the enterprise determines the most promising types of products, their strategic position in the market, directions of strategic support, and views of the strategy for different zones, as well as optimal strategic products. In marketing, strategic marketing activity or marketing plan defines the company's strategy. The choice of marketing strategy is made depending on the nature of the product and its position in the market. Marketing policy adapts to the nature of the supply and demand ratio.

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